

ACADEMIC STRESS AMONG TRIBAL AND NON-TRIBAL STUDENTS IN SATYA SAI DISTRICT OF ANDHRA PRADESH STATE

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Abstract

Aim: Academic stress among tribal and non-tribal students in Satya Sai district of Andhra Pradesh state. **Objectives:** To assess the difference between tribal and non-tribal students in academic stress. To find out the difference between boys and girls in academic stress and to examine the difference between government and private school students in academic stress. **Sample:** Sample of the investigation consists of 200 tribal and non-tribal high school students both boys and girls in Satya Sai district of Andhra Pradesh state was selected. **Tool:** Students Academic Stress Scale was developed and standardized by Srinivas and Kumar Reddy (1999) was used. **Statistical Analysis:** Mean, SD and 't' were calculated. **Conclusions:** Tribal students are experienced more academic stress than non-tribal students except teacher/pupil relationship/teaching methods; Boys are experienced more academic stress than girls and Private school students are experienced more academic stress than government school students except personal inadequacy and fear of failure.

Key words: Gender, type of Management, Academic Stress and Tribal & Non-Tribal Students.

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Introduction

India has the largest population of the tribal people in the world. Tribal's constitute 8.61% of the total population of the country, numbering 14.93 million (2011 Census) and cover about 15% of the country's total area. The government has been making efforts for the upliftment of tribal communities from the dawn of independence, so that they may compete with the non-tribal section. Provisions have been made in Indian constitution in this regard. Article-46: education, economic, social justice, and protection from exploitations of Scheduled Tribes. Article 330, 332 and 334 of the constitution of India provide for the reservation of seats for scheduled tribes in Lok Sabha and Raj Sabha. In accordance with Article 164 of the constitution, a minister for tribal welfare is appointed. Likewise, a good number of programmes, provisions, and schemes have been set up for the upliftment and amelioration of the conditions of tribal people. But still Tribal people are the one who are least developed and are most exploited.

The tribal students are the one with least exposure to the external world and with least facilities available to them but with a maximum support of their family and a healthy open environment to live in. With that situation, it would be worthwhile to check the academic stress of these students in comparison to the non-tribal students.

Academic Stress is an important factor accounting for variation in academic achievement. It also contributes to major mental health hazards, problems both physical and mental stress related diseases. Stress makes a significant contribution to the prediction of subsequent school performance and act as a negative predictor of academic performance in school children.

Academic stress refers to the pressure to perform well in final school examinations and competitive college entrance examinations that is experienced by students. For some students, the experience of academic stress leads to a sense of distress, which is generally manifested in a variety of psychological and behavioral problems. The experience of academic stress and adolescent distress has been identified and explored by many researchers.

Despite the fact that education is universally given a high priority, the academic institutions today do not show a motivating atmosphere. Students are often subjected to various stress related tests, examinations, excessive homework, teacher's biased

attitude, peer group pressure etc. The major challenges of children are: Poor retention and recall, lack of appreciation from their parents, school environment, personal anxieties, fear of teachers, examination phobia, perpetual insecurity, conflicting expectations from the parents and the society, the growing competition, fear of failure or success etc.

Literature Review

Chamely Khatun and Nur-E-Alam Siddique (2023) explored the perceived stress of tribal (Santal) and nontribal people in the Rajshahi district. The result revealed that ethnicity, gender, marital status and age play a significant role in the perceived stress. Park et al., (2023) found that students' limited coping skills can improve the impact of stress and diminish psychological well-being. Perceived stress is higher in female respondents than male respondents. Akhter et al., (2021) researched tribal and nontribal students. They suggested that tribal males get more social services than tribal females and tribal females get more stressed than males. examined that perceived stress among young adults. The result Ritika Joshi and Pragya Joshi (2021) of the research suggested that females have a high score on perceived stress. Graves et al., (2021) found that gender disparities in perceived stress and adapting among college students. They concluded that women revealed greater degrees of stress than their male counterparts. Bhattacharje et al., (2020) studied that stress among tribal and nontribal students. The result of the study revealed that the tribal students were significantly less stressed, but the non-tribal students showed significantly better coping. Subramani and Venkatachalam (2019) identified the sources of academic stress among higher secondary school students. The results showed that overall, academic environment was frequently reported to be major cause for academic stress than personal environment. The top five sources of academic stress were; parental expectations (96%), fear of failure in exams (96%), comparison with others (89.9%), grade competition with other student (89.4%), and too many tests (74.7%). Sweta Sonali (2018) revealed that students enrolled in science and commerce streams were found academically more stressed as compared to students enrolled in arts stream. However, there was no significant difference found between academic stress of students enrolled in science and commerce stream. It was also observed that girls and boys enrolled in science stream didn't vary significantly in their academic stress. Similarly, girls and boys enrolled in commerce stream didn't vary significantly in their academic stress while unlike science and commerce girls and boys enrolled in arts stream vary significantly in their academic

stress. Boys enrolled in arts stream were found academically more stressed than girls enrolled in arts stream. Ghosh (2016) students in private schools have more academic stress than their counterparts in government schools. Female students experienced higher academic stress than male students. Kaur and Kaur (2016) conducted a study on “Academic Stress in Relation to Emotional Stability of Adolescent Students”. Results revealed that there is no significant difference exist between academic stress (academic frustration, academic conflict and academic anxiety) with respect to gender but academic pressure showed significant difference between boys and girls. Girl participants are found to be more under academic pressure as compared to boys. Dhull and Kumari (2015) conducted a study on “Academic stress among adolescents in relation to gender”. Finding indicated that, there is significant difference between academic stress of male and female adolescents. Female subjects were found to be under more academic stress as compared to their male counterparts.

Objectives

1. To assess the difference between tribal and non-tribal students in academic stress.
2. To find out the difference between boys and girls in academic stress.
3. To examine the difference between government and private school students in academic stress.

Hypotheses

1. Tribal and non-tribal students would not differ significantly in their academic stress.
2. Boys and girls would not differ significantly in their academic stress.
3. Government and private school students would not differ significantly in their academic stress.

Methodology

Sample

Sample of the investigation consists of 200 tribal and non-tribal high school students both boys and girls in Satya Sai district of Andhra Pradesh state was obtained by using simple random sampling technique in the age group of 15-17 years.

Variables Studied

Dependent Variable

1. Academic Stress

Independent Variables

1. Ethnicity
2. Gender
3. Type of Management

Tool: Students' Academic Stress Scale: Students Academic Stress Scale was developed and standardized by Srinivas and Kumar Reddy (1999). It consisted of 40 items and sub divided into five components having eight items in each category. 1. Personal inadequacy (F1), 2. Fear of failure (F2), Interpersonal difficulties with teachers (F3), 4. Teacher/pupil relationship/teaching methods (F4) and 5. Inadequate study facilities (F5). Students' Academic Stress scale was score by giving weightages to the responses 0-1-2-3 and 4. The Maximum score 160 and Minimum score 40 obtained by adding the weightages on all these items. The rating scale in value of the score (five-point scale) varying from the response of "No stress, Slight Stress, Moderate Stress, High Stress and Extreme stress, with regard to degree of stress. A high score indicates more academic stress and low score indicates low academic stress. The test-retest method and it is 0.75 and the validity is 0.82.

Statistical Analysis

The obtained data was analysed statistically in order to test the hypotheses using Means, SDs and 't' test were calculated.

Results and Discussion

Table-1: Means, SD's and 't' value for the academic stress scores of Tribal and Non-Tribal students.

Dimensions	Ethnicity	Mean	SD	't'-Value
Personal inadequacy	Tribal	27.10	7.15	5.23**
	Non-Tribal	23.52	5.59	

Fear of failure	Tribal	28.87	5.35	4.10**
	Non-Tribal	25.86	6.19	
Interpersonal difficulties with teachers	Tribal	26.90	6.47	5.18**
	Non-Tribal	22.73	5.30	
Teacher/pupil relationship/teaching methods	Tribal	19.58	4.92	1.26 @
	Non-Tribal	18.30	4.86	
Inadequate study facilities	Tribal	21.50	5.95	4.42 **
	Non-Tribal	17.51	6.86	
Overall	Tribal	132.35	27.03	8.27 **
	Non-Tribal	114.11	25.34	

** - Significant at 0.01 level

@ - Not Significant

Significant 't' values of 5.23, 4.10, 5.18, 4.42 and 8.27 reveals that there are significant differences between tribal and non-tribal students with regard to their academic stress (Personal inadequacy, Fear of failure, Interpersonal difficulties with teachers and Inadequate study facilities). Where as insignificant 't' value of 1.26 reveals that there is no significant difference between tribal and non-tribal students with regard to their Teacher/pupil relationship/teaching methods. Hence, hypothesis-1 which stated that tribal and non-tribal students would not differ significantly in their academic stress is partially accepted by results.

It is proved that when comparison with mean scores, tribal students are experienced more academic stress (dimensions: Personal inadequacy, Fear of failure, Interpersonal difficulties with teachers and Inadequate study facilities) than non-tribal students. The remaining dimension is not significant i.e., Teacher/pupil relationship/teaching methods.

Table-2: Means, SD's and 't' value for the academic stress scores of boys and girls students.

Dimensions	Gender	Mean	SD	't'-Value
Personal inadequacy	Boys	29.72	7.15	4.11**
	Girls	26.44	5.59	
Fear of failure	Boys	31.37	5.35	3.62**
	Girls	27.52	6.19	
Interpersonal difficulties with teachers	Boys	25.05	6.47	2.30*
	Girls	23.38	5.30	
	Boys	21.74	5.27	5.23**

Teacher/pupil relationship/teaching methods	Girls	17.12	6.65	
Inadequate study facilities	Boys	28.47	5.18	2.51*
	Girls	25.23	8.32	
Overall	Boys	146.17	29.41	5.19**
	Girls	139.09	31.53	

** - Significant at 0.01 level

* - Significant at 0.05 level

Significant 't' values of 4.11, 3.62, 2.30, 5.23, 2.51 and 5.19 reveals that there are significant differences between boys and girls with regard to their academic stress (Personal inadequacy, Fear of failure, Interpersonal difficulties with teachers, Teacher/pupil relationship/teaching methods and Inadequate study facilities). Hence, hypothesis-2 which stated that boys and girls would not differ significantly in their academic stress is accepted by results.

It is proved that when comparison with mean scores, boys are experienced more academic stress (dimensions: Personal inadequacy, Fear of failure, Interpersonal difficulties with teachers, Teacher/pupil relationship/teaching methods and Inadequate study facilities) than girls.

Table-3: Means, SD's and 't' value for the academic stress scores of government and private school students.

Dimensions	Type of Management	Mean	SD	't'-Value
Personal inadequacy	Government	26.11	8.02	1.50@
	Private	25.90	9.23	
Fear of failure	Government	27.52	6.14	1.82@
	Private	26.38	8.47	
Interpersonal difficulties with teachers	Government	28.71	5.05	2.11*
	Private	24.56	7.17	
Teacher/pupil relationship/teaching methods	Government	23.46	5.29	4.24**
	Private	28.71	6.55	
Inadequate study facilities	Government	27.87	7.98	2.17*
	Private	29.43	5.11	
Overall	Government	128.29	29.27	7.23 **
	Private	123.57	28.12	

** - Significant at 0.01 level

* - Significant at 0.05 level

@ - Not Significant

Significant 't' values of 2.11, 4.24, 2.17 and 7.23 reveals that there are significant differences between government and private school students with regard to their academic stress (Interpersonal difficulties with teachers, Teacher/pupil relationship/teaching methods and Inadequate study facilities). Where as insignificant 't' values of 1.50 and 1.82 reveals that there is no significant difference between government and private school students with regard to their Personal inadequacy, Fear of failure. Hence, hypothesis-3 which stated that government and private school students would not differ significantly in their academic stress is partially accepted by results.

It is proved that when comparison with mean scores, private school students are experienced more academic stress (dimensions: Interpersonal difficulties with teachers, Teacher/pupil relationship/teaching methods and Inadequate study facilities) than government school students. The remaining dimension is not significant i.e., Personal inadequacy, Fear of failure.

Conclusions

1. Tribal students are experienced more academic stress in Personal inadequacy, Fear of failure, Interpersonal difficulties with teachers and Inadequate study facilities than non-tribal students except Teacher/pupil relationship/teaching methods.
2. Boys are experienced more academic stress in Personal inadequacy, Fear of failure, Interpersonal difficulties with teachers, Teacher/pupil relationship/teaching methods and Inadequate study facilities than girls.
3. Private school students are experienced more academic stress in dimensions of Interpersonal difficulties with teachers, Teacher/pupil relationship/teaching methods and Inadequate study facilities than government school students except Personal inadequacy, Fear of failure.

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